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THE INFLUENCE OF SKETCH QUALITY ON PERCEPTION OF PRODUCT-IDEA CREATIVITY

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the relationship between the quality of a sketch and how others perceive the creativity of the idea portrayed by the sketch. In this study, sketch quality is characterized through its line work, perspective, and proportions. Four different toaster ideas were each sketched by four people with different backgrounds and levels of sketching proficiency. Then, 360 reviewers ranked the toasters for idea creativity, referring to a set of 4 sketches—one sketch for each toaster concept. The level of sketch quality for each toaster concept was varied, being chosen from one of the 4 quality levels. Higher quality idea sketches were found to correlate with higher creativity rank, and lower quality sketches correlated with a lower creativity rank. A toaster idea portrayed with the highest quality-level of sketch was, on average, 2.6 times more likely to be ranked as the most creative idea within the given set of idea sketches. The results underscore the importance of how an idea is presented, and support the need for sketching instruction in engineering and design curriculum.

Keywords: sketching, idea evaluation, creativity

INTRODUCTION

In areas of design, engineering, and innovation, sketching plays an important role in generating, communicating, and evolving ideas (Schutze et al, 2003; van der Lugt, 2005; Goldschmidt, 1991; Ullman et al, 1990). In early-stage design, these sketches are often used to assess idea quality, and creativity is often an important consideration. This research attempts to better understand factors affecting the perceived creativity of an idea, building upon a recent study that found the clarity of a concept

sketch influences the perceived creativity of the idea the sketch portrays (Kudrowitz & Wallace, 2010). Specifically, this paper examines the effects of sketch quality on perceived creativity.

An understanding of how sketch quality affects perceived creativity of an idea may provide insight on how designers, engineers, and innovators can more effectively present their product ideas; this insight may also be applied to other disciplines that involve communication of creative works.

BACKGROUND

“In our culture, children, of course, draw like children, but most adults also draw like children, no matter what level they may have achieved in other areas of life... [D]rawing is not a vital skill for survival in our culture, whereas speech and reading are.” (Edwards, 1979)

In *Drawing on the Right Side of the Brain*, Betty Edwards reveals the common thought in Western culture that drawing is not a vital skill for survival. Counter to this thought, however, is the fact that drawing has been an ever-present tool of humanity; cave paintings dating back to 30,000 BP have been important in the communication and dissemination of ideas (Houston, 2004).

In the realm of engineering, design, and innovation, idea visualization and sketching is considered to be a vitally important form of communication (Schutze et al, 2003; van der Lugt, 2005; Goldschmidt, 1991; Ullman et al, 1990). Sketches are made to refine one’s thoughts, and to share ideas and evaluate the merit of concepts. Evaluation is based on a number of an idea’s attributes, but in early stage design, idea creativity plays an important role in concept selection.

Many studies have explored how to generate more creative ideas; a few have found that having more ideas is correlated with having more creative ideas (Kudrowitz and Wallace, 2010; Rietzchel et al, 2006; Diehl and Strobe, 1987). However, in addition to the creative merit of an idea in itself, the presentation of the idea may also affect the perceived creativity.

SKETCHING AS AN IDEA GENERATION TOOL

Sketching in design, engineering, and innovation often initiates the formation an idea in brainstorming processes. These sketches are generally quick line drawings, meant to convey the idea to other participants in the brainstorming session. Research has shown that these types of sketches are a substantial component of creativity in the design process (van der Lugt, 2005; Goldschmidt, 1991). As an individual sketches, he or she will extract new meaning from his or her sketch in-progress, which allows for the concept to evolve in different directions and to be built upon or reinterpreted. In a sense, it is a form of talking to oneself. This process of is referred to as the “dialectics of sketching” (Goldschmidt, 1991).

Similarly, other research suggests that as one sketches ideas, his or her concepts become more refined and can lead to a variety of novel ideas (Fish & Scrivener, 1990). More specifically, Goel describes two ways in which sketches help to advance ideas: lateral transformations, in which ideas transform into new ideas, and vertical transformations, in which ideas become more refined versions of the same idea (1995).

Since sketching is a central tool in early stage ideation, it is valuable to understand how the quality of the sketch might influence our perception of the merits of an idea.

TAXONOMIES OF DRAWINGS IN ENGINEERING AND DESIGN

Sketches evolve through three stages: explorative, explanative, and persuasive (Olofsson & Sjolen, 2005). A similar taxonomy is presented by Ferguson: thinking sketch, prescriptive sketch, and talking sketch (1992). A slightly more segmented drawing

classification is adapted from idsketching.com and presented in Figure 1 (2009).

Figure 1. From top to bottom, doodles, thinking sketches, presentation sketches and concept renderings (idsketching.com, 2009).

Doodles and personal communication sketches tend to be the genesis of a product concept. These sketches are used to quickly document an idea either for one’s own personal use in a design notebook or during a brainstorming session to communicate a concept. These sketches typically do not have any shading and are constructed using few loosely constructed lines. *Thinking sketches or thumbnail sketches* typically portray multiple variations of a concept and may focus on certain details. The concept is still vague at this stage of design, but a certain direction is being explored. These drawings are a bit more refined than doodles and are much cleaner in line work. Rendering is used sparingly.

Presentation sketches imply that a concept has been selected and drawings are made to communicate certain elements. These typically include non-photorealistic renderings with tone, perhaps a variety of views, and a means of depicting scale and interaction. *Concept renderings* could include photorealistic drawings or emotive sketches. On the engineering side, this could include part drawings, photorealistic CAD models, and drawings for manufacture.

In all of these progressive taxonomies, it is important to note that the sketch reflects the state of the design (Tovey and Porter, 2002). In other words, early sketches are unstructured, ambiguous, and vague to allow for creative exploration; as the design process progresses, both the design and the sketches become more detailed and refined.

Notice in Figure 1 that the sketches become more realistic and defined by increasing the amount of rendering and detail. This is the basis of yet another drawing taxonomy defined by McGown and Green (1998). In this classification, sketches are rated on a complexity scale of level 1 through level 5. Level 1 describes minimal monochromatic line drawings with no rendering or annotation. As the drawing becomes more detailed, rendered, and annotated, the level rating becomes higher.

In this study we focus on early stage design sketches. Depending on the taxonomy, they could be called exploratory sketches, thinking sketches, or low-complexity level sketches. We will refer to these sketches as conceptual sketches, as they represent brainstorming ideas that are not finalized and are in-progress.

Within this category of conceptual sketches, we need to develop more refined measures of sketch quality. These existing progressive taxonomies are more of a macro scale for the nature and level of detail, where in this study we look at a perpendicular axis of quality within a particular level of detail.

SKETCHING AND CREATIVE DESIGN

There is limited research on the importance of sketching in the early stages of design. Some studies

have found positive correlations between sketching ability and artistic creativity (Chan and Zhao, 2010; Chan and Chan, 2007), while others have found a positive correlation between the number of sketches made during a design process and product prototype outcome (Yang and Cham, 2007; Song and Agogino, 2004; Schutze et al, 2003). It has also been posited that drawing training in itself makes people more creative (Chan and Zhao, 2010). Few, if any, have explored how the quality or type of sketch influences the perception of the idea.

AESTHETICS AND PERCEIVED CREATIVITY

In a prior study evaluating product idea creativity, the clarity rating of a sketch was moderately correlated with the subjective evaluation of an idea's creativity (Kudrowitz & Wallace, 2010). In this same study, when comparing different sketches of the same general idea, the sketches that had higher clarity scores also had higher creativity scores. This can be seen in Figure 2, which depicts concept sketches for a toaster that optically detects if the toast is burning. Although all of the sketches represent the same idea, the sketches that had higher clarity scores also had higher creativity scores.

Figure 2. Creativity and clarity scores for four optical burn detecting toaster sketches (Kudrowitz and Wallace, 2010).

Other studies have also considered the effect of aesthetics on perception of existing products. In a study evaluating prototypes of telephone booths and computer cabinets, ratings of attractiveness were highly correlated with ratings of creativity (Christiaans, 2002). In another study involving the evaluations of existing lamps and chairs online, the category of affect, which included attractiveness, was found to be the strongest indicator of willingness to purchase (Horn and Salvendy, 2009). Bessemer included “well crafted” and “elegance” as metrics in her “Creative Product Analysis Matrix,” a tool for evaluating the creativity of a product (1998). When evaluating art (as opposed to consumer products), it was found that originality was an important factor in determining aesthetic quality (Hekkert and Wieringen, 1996). If aesthetics affects the evaluation of the final product or prototype, it can be hypothesized that aesthetics has an effect on the evaluation of the initial ideas.

EVALUATING CREATIVITY

Throughout this study we use Amabile’s Consensual Definition of Creativity: a product idea is creative if a group of independent reviewers subjectively agree it is creative (1982). If reviewers of ideas are not given a definition for creativity, they then use their own subjective definition to evaluate the ideas.

Amabile found that when dealing with common objects such as toasters, anyone may legitimately be considered an appropriate judge of creativity (1982). In this study, it is of interest to ensure that each test is ranked by an appropriate sample size of laymen reviewers. It is also of interest to ensure that the ideas are perceived to have the same creative ranking by the majority of laymen.

These ranking reviews can be made through an online survey in Amazon Mechanical Turk. Amazon Mechanical Turk is a web-based service (<http://www.mturk.com>) that allows any user to post tasks for any other user to complete for a small monetary payment. A recent study revealed that Mechanical Turk is a reliable source of experimental data and that the population of Mechanical Turk is at least as representative of the U.S. Population as traditional subject pools (Paolacci et al 2010).

EVALUATING QUALITY OF SKETCH

In this study, we describe sketch quality as a combination of mastery in line-work execution, correctness of perspective, and appropriateness or realism of proportions. The level of detail was maintained as a constant in this work since additional details might imply differing design features for the same concept. Also, only line drawings are considered. Several authors also provide detailed descriptions of elements that comprise sketch quality (Eissen and Steur, 2007; Olofsson and Sjolen, 2005; Alvarez, 2004).

In this study the majority of the sketches are “complexity level 2” as defined by McGown and Green (1998). Complexity level 2 indicates that the sketch is a monochrome line drawing with no shading; however, level 2 sketches may include different line densities made by varying pressures of a single medium. Complexity level 2 may also include a few brief annotations and motion arrows.

Line quality, as shown in Figure 3, can be described as a low amount of wiggle or tremor and a low amount of hash marks (short lines used to approximate a shape). These types of lines are perceived as sloppy. Construction lines, however, are helpful as they allow for structuring a drawing.

Figure 3. Examples of line work that are: clean, with tremor, and with hash marks (left to right).

Correctness of two-point perspective, as shown in Figure 4, can be described as the technical execution of perspective—having lines converge to a set of vanishing points, having vertical lines drawn vertically, having circular shapes drawn with correct ellipses, etc. A sketch becomes distorted when perspective is poorly executed. Shading and shadows should be placed correctly, if used.

Figure 4. Toaster sketches with correct 2-point perspective and incorrect 2-point perspective. Notice that lines converge in correct 2-point perspective.

Proportion, as shown in Figure 5, addresses the relative size of different features/dimensions within and object, and between different objects. Good proportions realistically reflect the intended artifacts. Items that have thickness are actually drawn with thickness. If an item is intended to fit into another item, it should appear that it could fit inside. Things that are intended to be symmetric are drawn symmetrically. Rounding corners may make a sketch look more realistic, but overly round corners will make it look unrealistic and cartoon-like.

Figure 5. Car sketches with correct proportions and incorrect proportions

Line quality, perspective, and proportions are all technical skills that are taught in schools of design.

Figure 6 presents six sketches of the same toaster idea drawn with decreasing quality of sketch. This order was independently agreed upon by two product designers with an extensive background in this area.

EXPERIMENT

This paper explores the relationship between the quality of a product-idea sketch and how others perceive the creativity of the idea portrayed by the sketch.

Figure 6. Horizontal Toaster Concept Sketched with Decreasing Levels of Quality (Line Work, Perspective, Proportions)

Four different product ideas were each drawn by individuals with varying levels of drawing ability: an industrial designer with many years of sketching training and experience; an engineering graduate student with limited sketching experience; an engineering student with no sketching experience, and a group of middle school students with limited to no sketching training. This produced a variety of sketches of the same set of ideas with similar levels of detail, but with varying levels of quality. Twenty-four sets of ideas were arranged so that each set presented the same four ideas, but each idea in the set was drawn with a different level of quality. 360 individuals independently evaluated the ideas in these sets on their creativity using an online survey.

SELECTING TOASTER CONCEPTS

Toasters were chosen as the general theme, building upon work by Kudrowitz and Wallace (2010) that also used toasters as a representative consumer product. A group of ten toaster ideas were chosen from this original study to represent a wide range of creativity. The written descriptions of these ten toaster ideas can be found in Appendix A.

To clearly represent a range of product-idea creativity, we asked three product designers to independently rank the ten ideas (based on word descriptions). Out of the ten concepts, the product designers ranked five of them in the same order based on idea creativity. The other five ideas were discarded for this experiment.

The descriptions of the selected five toaster ideas were then posted online and 100 laymen evaluated the creativity of the ideas using Amazon Mechanical Turk. For a majority of the 100 laymen, four of the five ideas fell in the same order as the experts'. A fifth idea was perhaps harder to understand in words, so the scores for that particular idea were

ambiguous. This fifth idea was discarded. Thus, four toaster ideas with a well-accepted creativity rank order was derived. All three product design experts and the majority of the 100 laymen agreed upon the creativity rank order for the 4 ideas, as listed in Table 1, in order of most creative to least creative.

1	Doodle Toaster	A toaster with a side panel that you can draw on; the drawing can then be toasted on to the bread.
2	Toaster/Coffee Maker	A combination toaster/coffee maker.
3	Horizontal Toaster	A horizontal toaster such that the bread is inserted and comes out horizontal to the ground.
4	Crumb Tray Toaster	A toaster that has a removable crumb tray at the bottom.

Table 1: The final four toaster ideas used in the sketching experiment. Ideas are listed from 1: most creative to 4: least creative.

CREATING TOASTER SKETCHES

Over twenty individuals with varying levels of sketching ability were independently asked to sketch the four toaster ideas based on the written

descriptions of the ideas. All sketches were made using the same drawing tools, and all individuals were given the same prompt (as described in Appendix B).

From the sets of sketches produced, two product designers evaluated the sketches on line quality, proportions, and perspective. Sketches were discarded if they included more detail or creative elements than presented in the descriptions. From this, four sets of each idea were chosen to represent a good variety in quality of sketch. The chosen sketches were made by: an industrial designer with many years of sketching training and experience (high quality sketches); an engineering graduate student with limited sketching experience (quality sketches); an engineering student with no sketching experience (very low quality toaster/coffee maker sketch), and a class of middle school students with limited to no sketching training (creating the rest of the low quality/very low quality sketches). The four toaster sketches of different quality for each toaster idea are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Four toaster concepts drawn at four levels of sketch quality

EVALUATING THE CREATIVITY OF SKETCHED IDEAS

All sketches were digitized, sized to similar scale, and presented in a survey using Amazon Mechanical Turk. The four different ideas were displayed in sketch format, and reviewers were asked to rank the ideas from most creative to least creative.

A baseline test that displayed the four ideas with the same sketch quality was first conducted with 200 people. In a second test, twenty-four sets of the sketches were arranged so that each set presented the same four toaster concepts, but different combinations of sketch quality. An example is shown in Figure 8. Online reviewers ranked the creativity of the sketched toaster ideas. Each reviewer received one of the 24 sets at random.

Figure 8. The survey as it appeared to survey-takers on Amazon Mechanical Turk. Details of the prompt are described in Appendix C.

The survey was made with the expectation to again use Amabile's Consensual Definition of Creativity to assess the creativity of the ideas. In this case, reviewers ranked the four ideas based on their subjective assessment of the ideas' creativity. No mention was made to quality or clarity of the sketches, so reviewers were not explicitly asked to take this into account when ranking the ideas.

Each reviewer was paid \$0.10 for completing the survey. In total, 360 different reviewers rated each sketch.

RESULTS

The findings support observations in prior work (Kudrowitz and Wallace, 2010) that sketch quality correlates with the perceived creativity of the idea. Over all four toaster concepts, the highest quality

sketches were more likely to be rated as most creative, with a normalized average creativity rating at 0.52 and a standard deviation of 0.29. The lowest quality sketches were more likely to be rated as least creative, with a normalized average creativity rating at 0.71, standard deviation of 0.27. Note that in this case, a lower numerical score indicates a higher creativity, since participants were informed that "1" was the highest creativity rank, and "4" was the lowest creativity rank. The normalized score, 0-1, is with relative to the lowest possible ranking (4).

In Figure 9, it can be observed that the creativity rank has a positive correlation with sketch quality. The creativity rank was obtained by taking the scores of all the high quality sketches and averaging them together, then all scores of the quality sketches and averaging them together, and so forth. Thus, regardless of the idea, it can be seen that sketch quality strongly correlates with perceived creativity, having $R^2 = 0.89$.

Figure 9. The perceived creativity of the ideas is plotted against sketch quality. Lower ranking corresponds to higher creativity. Bars are standard deviations.

Figure 10 (Appendix D) depicts the trend between sketch quality and perceived creativity in more detail, showing the number of people who gave a sketch a certain creativity rank. The larger the bar, the more the participants gave the sketch that particular score. Based on Amabile's Consensual Definition of Creativity, it can be concluded that the larger bars are the larger indicator of the creativity. Thus, the highest quality sketches are more likely to

be perceived as the most creative idea, independent of the idea. The very low quality sketches are more likely to be perceived as the least creative idea, again regardless of the particular idea. The high quality sketches were on average 2.6 times more likely to be ranked as the most creative idea when compared to sketch of the same idea drawn with lower quality. Lowest quality sketches were on average 2.5 times more likely to be ranked as the least creative idea when compared to the high quality sketch of the same idea. The sketches that were defined as "quality" and "low quality sketches" were generally ranked 2 or 3 more often, which continues to follow the trend of the other sketches.

Figure 11. Creativity of the ideas presented in a sketch vs. creativity of ideas presented in a written description.

In Figure 11, it is apparent that the overall order of the ideas' creativity is different than the creativity order when the written descriptions of the ideas were being evaluated. This result was similar to the baseline test that displayed the four ideas with the same sketch quality. The the average creativity of the written ideas were ranked:

Doodle > Cofee Maker > Horizontal > Crumb Tray.

The average creativity of the sketched ideas were ranked:

Coffee Maker > Doodle > Crumb Tray > Horizontal.

Indeed, while the general trend of the perceived creativity is still the same (the Doodle Toaster and the Combination Toaster/Coffee Maker were ranked as more creative than the Horizontal and the Crumb Tray Toaster) the baseline correlation between the perceived creativity of written and sketched ideas was $R^2 = 0.50$, only a moderate correlation.

Figure 12 provides the same linear fit as in Figure 9, but provides additional data on where the individual sketches lie in relation to this line. A sketch's average creativity is plotted and presented along with the associated sketch, providing a map of sketches to perceived creativity. Again, the lower left corner of the graph indicates a higher creativity and a higher sketch quality, while the upper right corner indicates a lower creativity and a lower sketch quality.

DISCUSSION

As observed, toaster ideas that were presented with a higher sketch quality were also ranked as having a higher creativity, with a correlation of $R^2 = 0.89$. The high quality sketches were on average 2.6 times more likely to be ranked as the most creative idea when compared to sketch of the same idea drawn with lower quality. This suggests that realistic proportions, correct perspective, and line quality are factors that influence the perceived creativity of an idea. One possible explanation is that ideas for products presented with high quality sketches may be more grounded in reality, as they are closer to the way we see the physical world around us. As high quality sketches of products need less interpretation to be understood as products, one can then focus on analyzing the creativity of the idea itself, rather than attempting to interpret the sketch in a meaningful way. It also might be easier for the reviewer to imagine what the product would be like to use in their own environment. Another possible explanation is that we simply prefer things that are aesthetically pleasing, and in this case, the quality of the sketch overpowers the quality of the idea.

However, this finding does not suggest that higher quaiy sketches are always preferred. According to Tovey and Porter's suggestions (2002), sketches that are of high quality as defined in this experiment can limit the exploration and evolution of the idea and more advanced visulaizations like CAD models may make the idea appear to be farther along the design process than it actually is. While it may be important for initial sketches to be exploratory and less refined, the idea can benefit from having high line quality, technically correct perspective, and appropriate proportions.

Figure 12. Mapping of each sketch's average creativity against the combined quality sketch's average creativity and fit line.

This study underscores the importance of presenting sketches in a similar quality and style in order to compare ideas without biasing results from differing sketch qualities. This especially applies to group idea generation sessions, where multiple people are contributing different ideas and sketches. The sketch variability could be a confounding factor and should be explored in further studies. This also applies when asking for people's preferences in market research studies.

This study suggests that the presentation of an idea is important in evaluating its creativity. Ultimately, the effort put into a high-quality sketch may positively effect the evaluation of the idea. Oppositely, creative ideas that have poor line quality, incorrect perspective or unrealistic proportions may be overlooked in favor of those ideas with better sketch quality, regardless of the creative merit of the idea in itself.

Sketching skills are not commonly taught to engineering students in the United States (Yang & Chan, 2007). The findings support the inclusion of

sketching in curricula for designers, engineers, and innovators, so that sketching ability can be elevated to a consistent level and biases caused by differing sketch quality can be reduced. As the capabilities of technology continue to expand, it may be beneficial to explore new ways of integrating technology into concept sketching and idea refinement.

It is also interesting to note the moderate-low correlation between the perceived creativity of the ideas when their written descriptions were ranked and when their sketches were ranked, with the baseline correlation being $R^2 = 0.50$. It is hypothesized that the unexpected correlation may have been due to a bias in the order in which the ideas were presented in the survey. The survey always presented the Combination Coffee Maker/Toaster idea at the top left, followed by the Crumb Tray Toaster, the Doodle Toaster, and the Horizontal Toaster. Survey takers may have been biased by seeing the first two ideas at the top of the page, which may account for the ideas being more creative than the bottom two, respectively. Future experiments may be improved by randomizing the order in which the ideas are presented on the screen.

However, it can also be hypothesized that the moderate-low correlation may not have been caused by any error at all; using sketching instead of writing as a medium to convey an idea may impact the perceived creativity of the idea by itself. This can imply that the nature of the medium causes the content to be processed differently, and may also imply that the interpretation of "creativity" differs across different media.

CONCLUSIONS

It was observed that a higher sketch quality correlates with a higher perceived creativity. The high quality sketches were on average 2.6 times more likely to be ranked as the most creative idea when compared to sketches of the same idea drawn with lower quality. Lowest quality sketches were on average 2.5 times more likely to be ranked the least creative idea when compared to high quality sketches of the same idea.

The results imply that line quality, correct perspective and realistic proportions are factors of a sketch that can influence the perceived creativity of an idea. This underscores the importance of selecting similar quality sketches when comparing ideas, and it also suggests possible implications for group brainstorming where wider level of sketching skills may be present.

The findings also support the inclusion of sketch training in curricula for designers, engineers, and innovators, so that sketching ability can be elevated to a consistent level and biases caused by differing sketch quality can be reduced.

Future experiments may explore how the presentation of ideas across different media can influence the ideas' perceived creativity levels, perhaps considering written media, using different typefaces and different textual information.

Finally, this study focused on the quality of sketches (line work, perspective and proportions) at a prescribed level of detail. Further studies could explore how the amount of detail, rendering and refinement affects perceptions of creativity. It is possible that ideas that have greater rendering and realism are easier to envision as a real product, but are also less open to interpretation.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

The following is the original list of ten toaster ideas. In the experiment, experts and non-experts ranked the creativity of these written ideas; out of the ten ideas, four of the ideas were ranked consistently. The four ideas were used in the final experiment.

- A toaster with an opening underneath and raised feet such that when the toast is finished, the toast can fall down onto a plate below.
- A horizontal toaster such that the bread is inserted and comes out horizontal to the ground.
- A toaster with a side panel that you can draw on; the drawing can then be toasted on to the bread.
- A toaster that has a removable crumb tray at the bottom.
- A combination toaster/coffee maker.
- A toaster built flush into the kitchen countertop.
- A clear toaster that allows you to see the toasting process.
- A toaster with a countdown digital timer indicating how much time is left until the toast is ready.
- A toaster that has enough slots for toasting a whole loaf of bread.
- A toaster that toasts bread as it moves through heating elements on a horizontal conveyor belt.

APPENDIX B

The following prompt was supplied to the participants providing the sketches for this experiment.

- Each of the sketches should be done on 8.5"x11" paper using only a fine-point black Sharpie, and the paper should be horizontally positioned (wider than it is tall).
- At the top of the page, please write the title of the toaster (given above) in large letters.
- There should only be one toaster on the paper (not multiple views of the same toaster, etc.); remember to draw large.
- You may annotate the sketch if desired, but try to say as much as possible using the sketch.
- The description of the concept must be accurately reflected in the sketch; please don't add extra features.
- Feel free to sketch as fast or as slow as you want, as long as you spend no more than 15 minutes on each sketch.

APPENDIX C

In the online survey provided in Amazon Mechanical Turk, reviewers received the following prompt before ranking the four presented toaster concepts:

“Four toaster ideas are displayed. Please take a look at the images, then rank them based on how CREATIVE the idea is. Rank them in order of most creative to least creative. You cannot give two ideas the same value; try to reason why one might be more creative than another.

Use the drop down menus next to the idea names to rank the respective images.

1 = Most creative Idea, 4 = Least creative Idea.”

APPENDIX D

Figure 10. Data of separate toaster concepts' perceived creativity against sketch quality. Perceived creativity is judged by the number of people who gave the sketch a particular rank; the data follows the trend that a higher sketch quality positively correlates with higher perceived creativity.

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